

Review

Significant Dynamics of Gilgit-Baltistan from Great Game to China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC)

Israr Hussain^{*1}, *Hu Lizhong*¹, *Iqtidar Hussain*¹, *Iqrar Hussain Qambari*²

¹*School of International Relations and Public Affairs, Shanghai International Studies University (SISU), No. 550 Dalian west Road, Postcode 200083, Shanghai, China*

²*Karakorum International University (KIU), District Gilgit, Pakistan*

***Corresponding author:**

Israr Hussain

Accepted: 15 June, 2020; Online: 23 June, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3905390>

Abstract: *The geopolitical factors have the actual deterrents which evaluate any region's fortune in international politics. The Gilgit-Baltistan (GB) geopolitics has been counted in global politics from the Great Game between Anglo-Russia in the nineteenth century. This research aims to examine that, what was the GB dynamics in the Great Game and now in the 21st century the GB geopolitical role for Sino-Pakistan relations in the context of China-Pakistan economic corridor (CPEC). The GB has a junction point in Asia, and the CPEC has the main tool to connect the Asian region. Thus the GB unclear constitutional status has the main obstacle for CPEC internally and externally. Internally the local mass strongly demands their rights according to the United-Nations (UN) resolutions, and externally India raised objections in the different international forums due to its disputed status as part of the Kashmir Issue. The CPEC has a bilateral economic plan, while the US and India is looking as strategic plans against their hegemonic position in the Indian Oceans.*

Keywords: Geopolitics; Gilgit-Baltistan; Great Game; Sino-Pakistan; CPEC; India & US,

Introduction:

In ancient times the GB was a central route for caravans. At the time, it was used to pass from Central Asia and China to reach Greek states as the nearest and safest place. Due to the ample availability of water, forests, and without population, there were no fears of robbery, which was very suitable for the journey (Naz, 2012). GB is the junction point between Central, South, and East Asia. It has located between Pakistan, China, Afghanistan, and both of Kashmir

(Pakistan & India) (P. Singh, 2013). In the 8th century, the great powers China and Tibet made many attacks on the region. The area was first time conquered by the hands of Chinese who are ruled 25 years (725-737 & 747 to 760), and then Tibetans ruled almost two centuries. The Tibetans elect their governor from the local people until the end of the 9th century. When the last Tibetan Governor Raja Shri Badat got killed, the nominal control of the Tibet came to an end because that time the Tibet was itself facing a decline (Ibid). After the death of Raja Shri Badat, the power was coming to Azar Jamsheed. He was a Persian prince who has come here to protect himself by the internal unrest in Iran. Raja Shri Badat was known for being very cruel, tyrant, and the cannibalism (Budlaf, 2012). Everyone in Raja Shri Badat's government, courtiers, ministers, and public as well his daughter Noor Bakht hated him and felt miserable. When the ministers of Raja Shri Badat got the news of the Prince Azar Jamsheed, they hid this secret from Raja Shri Badat. They arranged a secret meeting with Raja Shri Badat's daughter Noor Bakht, and they agreed mutually to get rid of Raja Shri Badat (Brown, 1998). After Shri Badat, Azar Jamsheed became the exclusive ruler, and Islam was spread in his era. The people, who belonged to local religious Shamanism and Buddhism, were converted into Islam.

Figure 1: The GB location in the region (E. M. Khan, 2017)

Materials and Methods

The qualitative research method has been used for this study. Qualitative Research is related to the justification of public phenomena, knowledge, and feelings of individuals producing subjective data. To maintain the validity of research, primary and secondary data sources have been used. As primary data sources, official documents, and the authorities' reports have been used. The articles of the journal, books, magazines, and the reports of the think-tanks have been used as secondary data sources. Mackinder's heartland theory of geopolitics is deemed appropriate for analyzing the theoretical spectrum of the geopolitical importance of the region of Gilgit-Baltistan.

The objective of this research is to analyze what was the importance of GB geopolitical in the Great Game and, after two centuries, what is the GB has a pivot position in new economic game CPEC. The GB was a focal point in Great Game, and now its significance has been highlighted in CPEC. In the Great Game, Russia needs GB to reach warm water, while China also has no access to link the Arabian Sea, and CPEC cannot be completed without GB. The Heartland theory has been selected to analyze the GB dynamical spot in Great Game and CPEC.

Heartland Theory and the Geopolitics of Gilgit-Baltistan

The Heartland theory has considered as fundamental concepts in geopolitical theories. The British scholar Halford John Mackinder has considered geopolitics founder by his geopolitical Heartland Theory. At the beginning of the 20th century, this geopolitical order was established when British dominance flourished. Mackinder elucidated how geographical elements have influences on state power. He explained three main points; the first World Island included with Eurasia and Africa. The second part consists of Heartland, and the third part has to contain America, Australia, and Malay Peninsula (Venier, 2019). Mackinder summarized his theory in these statements: who rules East Europe commands the Heartland; Who rules the Heartland commands the World-Island; who rules the World-Island commands the World (Mackinder, 1962). He thinks that the British have dominant power in sea routes. However, the new emerging powers, Germany and Russia, and their expected collation may have a significant threat to the British hegemonic role in the world (Dodds, 2007). The British thought that the Russian Empire has a countable threat for their hegemony. The Russian expansion policy in Central Asia has been a new challenge for Britain because, at that time, the Middle East and Subcontinent India

were the British colonies, and China was also in the British influence. Both powers' geopolitical struggling was the same ambition to control the world trade routes and resources land. This game was known as "Great Game," which started in the 19th century and ended at the beginning of the 20th century (Rubin, 2002).

The Great Game was based on geopolitical needs. The British want to control all trades routes and very conscious for these routes security as without safety these routes, it was not possible to exploit all colonial resources. The Great Game ended at the beginning of the 20th century due to WW-I (Dodds, 2007). After WW-II, the Great Game again started in new shaped the Cold War when the whole world divided into two blocs the Imperialist and the Communist. The US-lead the Imperialist bloc (instead of Britain) with the collation of Western Europe, and many other countries of the world and the USSR supported Communist bloc with the major collation of Eastern Europe, China, and some South American states. The US-lead collocation followed Mackinder's tentative plan during the Cold War Era and were successes to stop the spread of the USSR like Great Game, and the USSR lost her power in 1991 with her dismembering (Šćekić, 2016). The US also thinks that the new emerging fast-growing China is another hurdle for her global hegemony. The CPEC is an alternative channel for China to save access for the world instead of the South China Sea and the Indian Ocean. The GB significance has again increased by CPEC as like the Great Game, where Russia wants to reach the Arabian Sea.

The Arrival of Dogras in Gilgit-Baltistan

Historically, the GB is diverse from all other neighbors' based on its culture and tradition. From the 9th century, after freed from Tibetans to 1835, their neighboring states have not defied to occupy any small state. Because these states, despite many internal hostilities being united against external neighboring states (Russia, China, Tibet, Afghanistan, and Kashmir) (Zain, 2010). In the nineteenth century, the ruler's families of indoor distractions and other state attacks made them weak and forced them to take help from foreign states, and thus Sikhs of Lahore ruled here. The Dogra grip gradually stronger with the help of the British in the region; consequently, all local rulers lost their power and authority (Ali, 2004a). Thus, the last Tarah-Khan ruler of Gilgit has been killed by Raja of Yaseen Salman Shah, in 1822. After the kill of

Mohammad Khan, his daughter was ruled with the help of Raja Azar Khan (Puniyal) as Deputy Affairs of Gilgit, and after some years later, she got married (Nagar State) King Tahir Shah's elder son prince Krim Khan. The new ruler of Yaseen State Gohar Aman attacked Gilgit, and in this attack, the King of Nagar State has killed, and Raja Karim Khan fled from Gilgit with his wife, Princess Sahib Noma (Ibid). Now Karim Khan was traveled Lahore to seek help from the Sikh Empire. Mahajan Shere Singh sent his troops under the command of Colonel Syed Nathay Shah via Kashmir in 1842, who has defeated, Gohar Aman. However, unfortunately, the government has not fully control in Karim Khan; instead, a joint government was established as Karim Khan was helpless and comforted himself in silence (Hassnain, 1978). From 1848 to 1852, Dogra military remained in Gilgit after that they went back to Baltistan, and only one thousand troops were left in Gilgit. The Hunza and Yaseen, who took advantage of the situation and attacked Gilgit, led to victory. After the war, from 1852 to 1860, Raja Gohar Aman of Yaseen took the Gilgit's possession (Sing, 1986). In 1860 Maharaja Ranbir Singh sent 4000 troops to Gilgit under the command of Col Dev Singh. He achieved Gilgit very quickly because, after the death of Raja Gohar Aman, no particular personality was available for the leadership of all regional States (Ali, 2004b). The British forced to Maharaja for a status of the Gilgit Agency and allowed him to nominate their agent in 1877 (Sökefeld, 2005).

In the GB region, the Hunza and Nagar states were entirely freed from eternal's powers till 1891, and they made a plan to fight together against Dogra and British. The British and Dogra's control of the GB region was not completed without gaining victory in both states (Alder, 1963b). The British decided first to attack Nagar State. However, in the early Nilat Fort of Nagar, the British had to face substantial damage and extreme suffering in the war. At least they conquered Nagar State, and both state's rulers escaped to China (Knight, 1993). It has a tremendous achievement for both; the Dogra had been suffered significant financial loss in the last 51 years (1842 to 1891).

The Geopolitics of Gilgit-Baltistan and British Role in the Region

The British got tremendous achievement against Sikh in the Anglo-Sikh war 1845-1846. The British want to dismember the Sikh State for two main reasons; the first to weak Sikh emperor's strength and the second to create the new state as a buffer zone against neighboring

northern countries (Russia and China) (Madhok, 1972). They established a new state, including Jammu and Kashmir (J&K) region, as a buffer zone against northern powers. The British sold J&K to Dogra Rajput Gulab Singh for 75 million royal gold coins of the Sigh Emperor (Sökefeld, 2014). At that time, the GB region has consisted of six small states, Gilgit, Chilas, Yaseen, Hunza, Nagar, and Baltistan. Although based on the geographical importance of GB, the British focused intensely on these regions and wants the Gilgit region also used as an additional buffer zone. Russia wants to enter Indian hot water through Gilgit and Chitral.

On the other hand, she was moving towards the borders, as her relationship with Chitral and Hunza states increased day by day (Huttenback, 1975). The geographical importance of these areas the British was sent periodically many intelligent and courageous officers in the form of visitors. The most important was "*Mission Forsythe*," which visited the entire region except Kafiristan due to the opposition of Amir-e-Afghanistan. They realized that Amo Valley was to be separated from Chitral and Yaseen, where Burogal and Karambar passes were not tricky to smooth cross cannons and other emanations (Chohan, 1985). This information disturbed the British and to more investigate. They decided to send Captain Budliff (Ibid). Capt John Budliff investigated Gilgit, Yaseen, Hunza, Hindukush, and it all passes. He reviewed the whole region's geographical, linguistic, moral, and religious rituals as additionally. In this regard, he wrote the book "*The Tribes of Hindukush*," published in 1877 from Kolkata, which is still considered as the official book in terms of historical facts (Alder, 1963a). The British urged to Maharaja to give this area a particular agency category as to deploy their political agent. John Budliff was posted as a special duty officer to Gilgit. In 1879 with the Gilgit Agency's announcement, he was appointed as a regular political agent. Since Dogra's government forcibly made an agreement with the British but kept high conditions and many hurdles on the way, even the public have not liked the British. This reason Britain failed to get the results from the establishment of the Agency (Chaudhary, 2015). However, the governments of India decided to withdrawal the agency and insured to Maharaja that the government of India fully authorized when required they can move. It was also expected that Kashmir would provide the mandatory information to India's government, for instance, her absence (Ali, 2012a).

Restoration of Gilgit Agency

The British once again found certain conditions in northern borders in 1889 and decided to re-establish the Gilgit Agency. After the eviction of political agents of Gilgit Agency, the Amir-e-Afghanistan Abdul Rahman claimed on Chitral, Swat, Bajaur, and other adjoining tribal territories. He sends a letter to Maharaja of Kashmir on 20th March 1881 that the British have not right to interfere in these areas, as Afghanistan became the second big headache for British (J. Singh, 1995). After the withdrawal of the British from Gilgit, Russia started moving slowly towards the north of Afghanistan, and finally, in 1885, they were able to capture on Pinjhra (Chohan, 1985). In those days, many Russian military officers were visited Hunza State several times in the shape of visitors. Similarly, in 1888 Hunza and Nagar State stood against Kashmir, and their two thousand troop has evacuated Dogra forces form Chalet, Chaprot, and Nomal valley, which distance to Gilgit city was only 20 km (Knight, 1893) In light of the above facts, the governments of India re-establish Gilgit Agency in April 1889. Col Durand has appointed as a Political Agent and, both governments were agreed to jointly bear all expenses of the agency (Huttenback, 1975).

Col Durand visited first Nagar on 9th August 1889 and later visited Hunza, while both states were refused to access for the British to build a road from Gilgit to Russia and China borders (Ibid). The British and Dogra make a joint plan against their last hurdle in 1891 with heavy emanations, but they had to face extreme difficulty in Nagar Nilat Fort. Eventually, after some months of continuous struggle against them, they conquered both states through the betrayal of the local British traitors (Durand, 1974). The other side unclear border situation with neighbors was not suitable for the political stability of the relevant areas. Therefore after careful thought, the British, Russia, and Afghanistan were willing to determine the formation of borders. On 12th November 1893, Sir Mather Durand Foreign Secretary of India has agreed with Afghanistan and decided that a Durand Line should be named on the completion of borders between Afghanistan and British India (Ibid). This agreement was a British trick that drew abounds on these areas. Still, there are some of the places which were forced to be in the other country's control. That is a clear example of the Wakhan Corridor, which total length is 350 km and the width is 18 to 65 km. The main reason for giving the area of Gilgit Agency to Afghanistan was to get rid of British Indian territory to Russia. Those who well aware of the areas know the British blunder for their interest, and the maps have shown that is no angle Wakhan Corridor become part of Afghanistan (Omrani, 2009). They got great success by getting

free from Russia, and now between these two powers, the Wakhan Corridor was formed a buffer zone. This agreement was of significant progress for Britain; however, they were not ignoring the border situation for a single moment (Fraser-Tyler & Gillett, 1967). They had to adapt to every type of tricks to keep a strong influence on Afghanistan and China. Both superpower spies went for adventurers in the disguise of traders and used to visit, which was part of the Great Game, the Gilgit Game (Mustafa, 1972).

Figure 2: The Geographical Significance of Wakhan Corridor (MD, 2017)

The purpose of excellent defense against neighbor's Indian government approved a local scout force "Gilgit Scout" in 1916 whose expenses will be endorsed jointly by Maharaja and British government. Its total strength was 600, divided by eight companies, and after the training, different posts had set up (Ali, 2012b). While the British were more freighted, they accept all measurements to protect the northern borders when the Russian invasion in Xinjiang China in 1934. Therefore in 1935, the Viceroy of India pressurized Maharaja to take Gilgit on lease for 60 years. The agreement was made on 26th March 1935, and the British gained full control after leasing the Gilgit Agency (Sökefeld, 2005).

Figure 3: The GB and Kashmir during the Dogra regime (Jaibans, 2015).

The Revolution of Gilgit and the British Plot

The Gilgit State was established in the nine century, and the local people of Gilgit faced many tortures from the beginning when there were local Kings Governments. They were the whole and sole. In 1842, when Dogra came here, more horrors of violence and suffering were to be bear by people. The period from 1846 to 1893 counts to suffering for Gilgit because at that time, due to attacks on Hunza Nagar Chilas, Darail, and Warshigam, the Gilgit was a victim of extreme impoverishment and unrest (Sōkefeld, 2005). Dogra did persecution more than 100 times as compared to local Kings, and also religious-extremism was promoted the local people more hatred against Dogra. While local people even hated the British, as their help Dogra got the array of governance throughout the region. However, the British reputation has been changed due to their batter administrative management as compared to Dogra when they took Gilgit on lease for 60 years in 1935. The British made the most implemented system of all things, especially about the settled lands, and there was a significant reduction in the revenue collection. Besides, local people got vast job opportunities in the form of Gilgit Scouts, which raised people's dignity and awareness (Rasool, 2004). The British could not defend this famous region

without wisely tried to win people's hearts. The people have seen the first time some fundamental human rights, which were the leading cause that locally admired and given lots of respect to the British.

When the British parliament approved the 3rd June 1947 partition plan of Subcontinent that time 562 states were existence in Subcontinent under the British authority, and they have to choose to merge into Pakistan or India. Therefore the British returned Gilgit Agency has controlled Maharaja on 1st August 1947. Maharaja announced Gilgit Agency into the province, and Brigadier Ginsara Singh was nominated as Governor (Watson, 1966). The local peoples were more oppressed against Maharaja by his governor's controversy of being over dry, biased, and hated behavior by local employees. The Gilgit Scout considered these measures as the risk for their jobs and other privileges given by the British. They have determined that if Maharaja announces an independent state or attaches with Pakistan, then no way of revolt. After the formation of the sovereign state, the population here is predominantly Muslim; as a result, they will be celebrating their demands. The second option in case of facilitation with Pakistan then there will not be injustice with them. However, if Maharaja appends India, then they have no way apart from revolting to free the area (M. S. Khan, 2000). The Gilgit Scouts officers set up in different meetings among themselves, and to thought entirely on these three situations formed an action. The British were in favor of dividing the Dogra colonial province (Gilgit-Baltistan) into two parts, one part includes Astor, Baltistan, and Ladakh districts with connected Kashmir Ministry, and merged into India. The other part will consist of Gilgit Chilas, Darail, Yaseen, Nagar, and Hunza, whose borders are connected with Afghanistan, Russia, and China to be free from Dogra, and join Pakistan. For this tremendous secret plotting, specifically, two British officers (Major William Alexander Brown and Captain Mathewson) were entered into Kashmir Maharaja's force for two years service (Sōkefeld, 2005). Along, Major Brown has close ties with the Hunza and Chitral states and behind had hidden support of Sir George Cunningham Governor NWFP (Pakistan), Col Bacon political agent of Khyber Agency, and General Grace Chief of Army Pakistan. These British officers did different planning to adjoin Gilgit into Pakistan. For the beginning of this planning, they named the ***Operation Datta Khel*** that will start at the right time, and Major William has full authority. The Maharaja's Army was the biggest hurdle in the way of the British plan. However, Major Brown started the procedure with high intelligence and craftiness to stop Maharaja Army in Bounji Garrison 26 miles away from Gilgit

city. The other hand spread propaganda in Gilgit Scouts against Maharaja and Governor so they cannot create hurdles in his project. The Gilgit Scouts were all non-commissioned officers, who have belonged to King's family, and at any time, their simplicity could take advantage. The British did not want that Gilgit with such good geography should join in any cost with Kashmir, and India. According to them, Gandhi, Nehru, Sardar Patel, along with other personalities of Congress Party India has a strong supporter of communist ideas. Russia's direct borders connection with India means losing all South Asia permanently, and Russia can easily access the warm waters of the Arabian Sea. Hence for Britain and America to catch up with Russia regarding trade and ships can be a big challenge (Rasool, 2004). The Maharaja and his Prime Minister wanted to be an independent state while the British wanted the whole area of Kashmir to be divided into two pieces. Therefore, the two British officers entered Maharaja's Army and were appointed as commandant and deputy commandant in Gilgit Scouts. Major William Brown was selected very carefully for the post of commandant in Gilgit Scout because he had provided services for more than three years (1943 to 1946) before in Gilgit. He was very famous for his convincing power, intelligence, wisdom, and durable decision power. Major Brown mentioned in his book "*The Gilgit Rebellion*" and has compared himself to Lawrence of Arabia. The latter was famous in the British Army by playing a pivotal role in separate parts of the Ottoman Empire in 1923 (Ibid).

The Gilgit situation was critical and going worsen day by day after the arrival of Governor Gansara Singh since 1st August 1947, as liked critical conditions were dominated on the whole Subcontinent. The British hypocritical cause difficulties to a great extent, and a clear case of Kashmir's problem. The Governor Sir George Cunningham and Col Bacon Political Agent had been full backing of foolish Chief Minister (CM) NWFP Abdul Qayum Khan. He accepted the British officers well to entered tribesmen in Kashmir to fighting with Hindu Maharaja for the sake of Kashmiri Muslim. Tribesmen came on Kashmir on 22nd October 1947; Maharaja was afraid and requested India to help fight Pathan Tribesmen. India got a marvelous opportunity to enter her troops in Kashmir and defeated Tribesmen(M. I. Khan, 22nd October 2017). In Gilgit, Major Brown was waiting for the right time for execution on *Operation Datu Khel* through "Gilgit Scout." The entire situation was changed on 31st October night when Gilgit Scout encircled Governor House on the advice of Dogra Army's Muslim officer Major Hassan Khan. The next day, the governor was arrested at 10 am and announced the independence of

"the Islamic Republic of Gilgit State." Now Gilgit got rid of Dogra, but Major later Col Hassan Khan was the biggest hurdle on the way of Major Brown. In 1937, Hassan Khan took Commission in Maharaja Army, and he was the second person in Gilgit Agency after Lieutenant Colonel Ahsan Ali. Hassan Khan was the only member of the Gilgit who has deeply know the circumstances of Kashmir and Gilgit and well aware of the international situation after WW-II (M. H. Khan, 2002).

Col. Hassan was the most significant impediment for the British officer Major Brown because if any officer throughout the region could stand up in front of Major Brown, it was Col Hassan. Col Hassan, with his colleagues, formed a transitional Government Majlis-e-Shurah (Council). A retired Subedar Raja Shah Raees Khan was President, and Col Hassan Khan was appointed as a Commandant of Gilgit Scouts and Independent Force, which consisted of the Maharaja's rebel soldiers' Army. The other members of Council liked Captain Saeed Durrani Deputy Commandant, Lt. Ghulam Haider Treasurer, Raja Hameed Khan Police Inspector, Subedar-Major Babar Khan as a Quarter-Master. In contrast, the Council's members insist that Col Hassan Khan has accepted Major Brown as an advisor (Alam, 2003). Although Major Brown was successes his plots against Col Hassan that includes; Hassan wants Shia State, which will be dangerous for other sects of Muslims. Alternatively, Hassan wants to stable government and later shoots all the Kings on Gilgit's Bridge and throws their bodies into the Indus River, because they did not help for independent revolt, etc. In this way, the main purpose of Major Brown was to add Gilgit in Pakistan as British wishes, not Hassan or local people's wishes, so that the British can play Gilgit cards according to their future concerns. On 16th November 1947, the Gilgit State-controlled was taken by Sub-Magistrate Mohammed Alim Khan, the first Political Agent from the Government of Pakistan. However, that time Col Hassan put a condition that Political Agent cannot approve any order without concern with the local Council, which has formed on 1st November 1947. The Political Agent Muhammad Alam and other foolish Council members came against Col Hassan due to Major Brown's influences, and conspiracies. Thus, six decades later, Gilgit has a constitutional limbo neither part of Pakistan nor part of Aazad (Independent) Jammu and Kashmir State. However, rule Pakistan authority directly without local representation in any Central Institutes like other Provinces of Pakistan, and India claimed it is her territory occupied by Pakistan (Nazir, 2005).

The Gilgit-Baltistan: A Constitution Limbo from 1947 to Onward

Table 1: Constitution status from 16th November 1947 to onwards (Assembly)

Era	Details
1948	Imposed FCR
1850	Transfer authority from NWFP Governor to Minister of Kashmir Affairs (KANA)
1964	Fundamental Democratic System introduced by President General Ayoub Khan
1967	Developed a post of Resident and its office declared as headquarters of Local Government
1969	Northern Areas advisor Council consist of 8 members by nominated from bureaucracy
1974	Administrative reform and demolished FCR
1975	Change the title Northern Areas Advisory Council to Northern Areas Council and increased seats from 8 to 16
1977	GB declared in Marshall law E-Zone. Before two Marshall law's GB was not included
1994	The Northern Areas Council first-party base general election under LFO
1999	The 2 nd general election under LFO-II and authorized legalizations on 49 subjects
2004	The 3 rd general election under LFO-II and given the title NA. Legislative Assembly instead NA. Legislative Council
2007	The post of Chief Executive was approved
2009	Gilgit-Baltistan Order 2009
2018	Order 2018 passed but local judiciary and peoples rejected
2019	The Supreme Court of Pakistan rejected Order 2018 and declared a disputed treaty and ordered to Federal Government to give fundamental rights under the UN Resolutions.

The GB is unfortunate land in Asia, which got independent from the Dogra regime on 1st November 1947 and accessioned with Pakistan in the name of Islam on 16th November 1947. After Accession with Pakistan, her new miserable story started, continuing still in the 21st century. Pakistan bureaucracy, Judiciary, Army, and Politicians ignored the region and considered the area for their only benefits. The Government of Pakistan ruled GB through Frontier Crimes Regulations (FCR) from 1948 to 1974, where all fundamental rights are dismissed. The FCR was made by the British for Federal Tribal Administrated Areas (FATA) in 1902 to control these unrest tribal regions brutally (Jones, 2002). Pakistan included GB again

Kashmir Issue due to greediness of vote in plebiscite according to UN resolutions 1948. The Indo-Pak agreed for the referendum in Kashmir, according to Kashmiris, well to join Pakistan or India under the UN. In the beginning, the region declared under the Governor of NWFP. However, Pakistan made another mistake to make an agreement with Azad (Independent) Jammu and Kashmir (AJK) leaders on 22nd April 1949 and taken GB controlled under the Federation. This was the infamous Karachi agreement where actual possessor (Assembly) was ignored entirely still as of today (P. Singh, 2013). From Independent 14th August 1947 to onward Pakistan made three constitutions 1956, 1962 and 1973, but was not mentioned GB as the Part of Pakistan. While, its facts, that GB was not part of Kashmir in history, before the invasion of Dogra from 1835 to 1947. The GB people free region from Dogra passion with their well without any external support, and after 16 days independent, the local government herself voluntarily accessioned with Pakistan. However, unfortunately, after 72 years, the GB region has not part of Pakistan and has a miserable situation by constitutionally. As it neither, part of AJK State or Pakistan, but the Federal Government ruled as a colonial system (Bansal, 2013).

Geopolitical Consequences of Gilgit-Baltistan for CPEC

Geopolitics of a country plays a vital role in her financial, economic, agricultural, and political sectors. Pakistan's geographical location is unique in Asia, where East, West, South, and Central Asia are connected. For that reason, superpowers continuously tried to put their shadow on Pakistan, but all powers failed to benefit from her geographical position (Javaid & Jahangir, 2015). The world's most rapidly growing economy, China, planned to get benefit from Pakistan's geopolitical location. Thus they make a \$ 46 billion CPEC plan through highway, railway, and energy pipeline system; both will permanently connect (Ahmad, Fatima, & Bowra, 2017). The GB has a significant role in the Asian region due to her geopolitical position. It is only that part of Asia, where three Asian regions (East, South, and Central Asia) are connected. It borders attached with Indian controlled Jammu and Kashmir, China, Afghanistan, and after Wakhan Corridor 18 to 65 km distance with Tajikistan (Sood, 2016). The geopolitical importance of GB has played a vital role in the Pak-China relations epically CPEC project. In this regard, GB has an essential figure of regional geopolitics. The CPEC has boosted her covered geopolitical significance in international radar, and it will be more highlighting with completion of CPEC road and the railway line from Gwadar Pakistan to Kashgar China at 2030. The CPEC has multidimensionality beneficial for Sino-Pak economies. It will also be the tremendous prospects

for the Central Asian landlocked states to secure access for the Arabian Sea(Wolf, 2016). China has golden achievements through CPEC; alternative passage to avoid Malacca Conflicts, nearest point to reach the Middle East, and her Western region will be making another economic hub to connect the regional countries. Pakistan can enjoy geostrategic, and geo-economics benefit from Gwadar Port. As geostrategic, Gwadar will be a second naval base where China has given eight submarines under CPEC. Economically, she can easily access to the international market, vast employment opportunities, foreign investments, and corridor income (Hussain & Khan, 2017).

The GB has a unique status for Pakistan's position in Asia, where she can link with her long-lasting friend China, and the other connects with Central Asia. The KKH, which has considered the eighth wonder of the world, 427 km portion, has consisted of GB, and consider friendship corridor between Sino-Pak. It plays a tremendous role in stronger bilateral geostrategic and economic relations, especially after the 90s. There is no option for CPEC to enter Pakistan without GB because China only has a border with Pakistan. Nevertheless, India has an objection to CPEC through GB, she claimed on GB as her integral part. She argues Maharaja of Kashmir's accession with India on 26th October 1947, and that time the GB was under Kashmir State. However, Pakistan has occupied Kashmir's two regions AJK, and GB illegally. Pakistan rejects the Indian concern, as well as China, supports the Pakistani stance on International forums. India also was not accepted China's request to join BRI while except her all regional states joint BRI (Kumar, 2017). India again raised objections on CPEC via GB in a different forum. The Indian PM Narendra Modi also threatens Pakistan about GB, and Balochistan during his 70 national anniversary's speech in 2016 (Sandhu, 15th August 2016). India has funded many religious and Baloch separatist groups to attacks on Chinese workers in Pakistan. From 2017 to 2019, these terrorists made many attacks in Chinese workers but were not a success by the quick response of security personals in different attacks (Ahmed, 12th May 2019). On the other side, America has worried about CPEC. She wants to fully control the Asia Pacific Region with the help of India because Indian dominance has a unique position in South Asia by her geopolitics, significant population, and emerging economy. The US though the CPEC has direct hit her policies in the region as it is given a safe route to China to avoid all conflict in Malacca Dilemma and cheapest way for import, export by less distance for the rest of the world (Bijian, 2005). The US Deputy Assistance Secretary of State for South and Central Asia Alice Wells briefly expressed the US reservation on CPEC. She suggested to Pakistan for

with drawl to CPEC on her speech addressed in Washington DC on a conference at 21st November 2019 (Embassy, 21st November 2019). Pakistan Foreign Office spokesperson Aisha Farooque strongly rejected all allegations about CPEC project transparency, high debt ratio, employment opportunities, and developments (Report, 24th January 2020).

Conclusion:

The GB has unique geopolitical significance from ancient times while its importance has been increased in the nineteenth century with the rivalry between Great Britain and Russia. After being free from Tibet in the nine century, the state gradually lost his dignity and divided it into many small states, but all states were united against foreigner attacks. In 1835 the Sigh Empire conquered the Baltistan State territory Ladakh with the request of the State prince against his father. In 1842 the Gilgit State Princes and her husband requested to Sigh Empire free Gilgit possession by Yaseen State. When, the British won the last war in the Subcontinent against Sigh Empire in 1845-46 the decision to make a buffer zone against Russia. The British sold Jammu and Kashmir region to old Sigh Emperor Jammu Governor Gulab Singh and agreed that the new state would be helpful for the British against the northern borders of Subcontinent. The British and Russian struggle for geopolitical pivot areas in Central Asia was called "the Great Game," which started from the beginning of the nineteenth century and ended after WW-I. The Gilgit came on international political radar from the nineteenth century when Russia wanted to reach the warm waters of India through Gilgit. The British pushed to Dogra in the region towards completion of their objects because geographically, the area was the most significant threat by Russia for which they shut the gates of these areas. The British knew that Afghanistan was under the influence of Russia, and the northern Indian border may cause a big thread for them. They have two causes against Russia the first to save India and the second save to all navy installments on the Persian Gulf and its surroundings. The British fought three wars against Afghanistan (1839, 1880, and 1919) to end Russian influence but was not entirely successful in achieving their aims. Since the British were closely monitoring the Russian activities on these borders, the agency systems, border demarcation with Afghanistan, hand over Wakhan Corridor to Afghanistan, and establishment of Gilgit Scout for strong defense were extraordinary measures to protect the region. After 3rd June 1947, the Subcontinent dismember announcement the British make another plan regarding Gilgit Agency by her geopolitical position. The British want to

separate Gilgit Agency from Kashmir and joint Pakistan through revolt against Maharaja. According to their views, the Gilgit accessioned with Pakistan will cut to link the chances of Russian with India, which can be another thread in the future for Britain and new superpower America. They were successful in their plots to diverting the Gilgit' revolution, and still, after seven decades, the GB region faces the colonel system by the British influences in Pakistani bureaucracy.

The CPEC is a tremendous achievement between Pak-China relationships. The GB dynamic role has again increased in international radar by the CPEC as its pilot project of the Chinese BRI plan. Thus the US worried about Chinese influence in the region as she still practices all geopolitical theories, especially the Heartland theory, as an underlying theme to maintain her dominancy globally. Before 1991 the Russian collapsed; the US used her all proxies to stop USSR for access to warm water. Thus she wants to stop China from reaching the Persian Gulf via Gilgit. The other side India has border conflicts with Sino-Pak since 1947 and has fought many wars with them. She has objections to CPEC passing through GB as the region disputed status between Indo-Pak. In all these circumstances, Pakistan has only a chance to null and void all reasonable objections on GB by taking substantial measures about its constitutional status according to the UN resolutions. It is also a strong demand for the GB mass to Pak Government gives constitutional rights until the Kashmir Issue solution on the light of UN resolutions. If Pakistan neglect or more dallied, like the last 72 years then, it will be unbearably lost for Pakistan's dignity, and CPEC cannot be completed.

Reference:

- Ahmad, H. Z., Fatima, S., & Bowra, Z. A. (2017). CPEC 2015: A Review of Proposed Opportunities and Significance. *Paradigms*, 11(2), 178-183.
- Ahmed, A. (12th May 2019). Gwadar hotel attack; Testing time for Prime Minister Imran Khan, *World Asia*. Retrieved from <https://gulfnnews.com/world/asia/pakistan/gwadar-hotel-attack-testing-time-for-prime-minister-imran-khan-1.1557664066087>
- Alam, S. (2003). *Tehreek-e-Pakistan Mu Shamali Alakajat Ka Kirdar (Role of Northern Areas in Pakistan Movement)*: Business Forum Blue Area Islamabad, p. 88.
- Alder, G. J. (1963a). *British India's northern frontier, 1865-95: a study in imperial policy*: [London]: Longmans, p. 119.
- Alder, G. J. (1963b). *British India's northern frontier, 1865-95: a study in imperial policy*: [London]: Longmans, pp. 228-229.

- Ali, U. (2004a). *Gilgit ki Roge Kahani (The Sorrowful tale of Gilgit)*: Maqbool Academy Lahore, p. 19.
- Ali, U. (2004b). *Jalwa-e-Karakoram (The glory of Karakoram)*: Maqbool Acaem Lahore, p. 141.
- Ali, U. (2012a). *Gilgit Ka Inqaleebn: 1947 (The Gilgit's Revolution:1947)*: Sang-e-Meel Publications Lahore, pp. 42-43.
- Ali, U. (2012b). *Gilgit Ka Inqaleebn: 1947(Gilgit's Revolution, 1947)*: Sang-e-Meel Publications, Lahore, pp. 68-80.
- Assembly, G. Gilgit Baltistan Assembly. from <http://gba.gov.pk/brief-history/>
- Bansal, A. (2013). Gilgit-Baltistan an appraisal (Manekshaw Paper No. 37). *New Delhi: Centre for Land Warfare Studies*.
- Bijian, Z. (2005). China's" Peaceful Rise" to GreatPower Status, getting the facts right. *Foreign Affairs Magazine*.
- Brown, W. A. (1998). *The Gilgit Rebellion, 1947*: Ibex, p. 09/ pp. 115-144.
- Budlaf, J. (2012). *Hindukush ky Qabail (Tribes of the Hindukush)* North Publications Gilgit, p.178.
- Chaudhary, M. A. (2015). Changing Political Dynamics in Gilgit-Baltistan: A Socio-Historical Perspective. *Pakistan Journal of History and Culture, Vol.XXXVI, No.2*.
- Chohan, A. S. (1985). *The Gilgit Agency 1877-1935*: Jumhoori Publications Lahore, pp. 40-68/ 65-68.
- Dodds, K. (2007). *Geopolitics: A concise introduction*: OUP Oxford.
- Durand, A. (1974). *The making of a frontier*: Akademische Druck-und Verlagsanstalt, p. 226.
- Embassy, U. (21st November 2019). Ambassador Wells' remarks on the China Pakistan Economic Corridor. from <https://pk.usembassy.gov/ambassador-wells-remarks-on-the-china-pakistan-economic-corridor/>
- Fraser-Tytler, W. K., & Gillett, M. C. (1967). *Afghanistan: A Study of Political Developments in Central and Southern Asia*, p. 188.
- Hassnain, F. M. (1978). *Gilgit, the Northern Gate of India*: New Delhi: Sterling, p. 27.
- Hussain, S., & Khan, M. A. (2017). CPEC; A Roadmap of Region's Development. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences, 11(2)*.
- Huttenback, R. A. (1975). The 'great game' in the Pamirs and the Hindu-Kush: The British conquest of Hunza and Nagar. *Modern Asian Studies, 9(1)*, 1-29.
- Jaibans, S. (2015). Pakistan Occupied Kashmir and Gilgit-Baltistan. *Indian Defence Review*.
- Javid, U., & Jahangir, A. (2015). Pakistan-China strategic relationship: A glorious journey of 55 years. *Journal of the Research Society of Pakistan, 52(1)*.
- Jones, O. B. (2002). *Pakistan: Eye of the Storm* (new Delhi: Penguin Books India (P) Ltd, p. 70.
- Khan, E. M. (2017). *The role of geography in human security: a case study of Gilgit-Baltistan*. National Defence University (NDU) Islamabad.
- Khan, M. H. (2002). *Shamsheer Say Zanjeer Tak (From Sword to Chain)*. : K-2 Group of Publications, p. 28.

- Khan, M. I. (22nd October 2017). Partition 70 years on When tribal warriors invaded Kashmir, *BBC News*. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-41662588>
- Khan, M. S. (2000). *Gilgit Scouts*. : North Publications Gilgit, p.115-127332.
- Knight, E. F. (1893). Where three empires meet. *Vanguard Books, Lahore*, pp. 345-350.
- Knight, E. F. (1993). *Where three empires meet*: Vanguard Books Lahore, pp. 440-453.
- Kumar, V. (2017). India's Gilgit-Baltistan Problem–Part One: Pakistan's Dependence on Gilgit-Baltistan.
- Mackinder, H. J. (1962). *Democratic ideals and reality a study in the politics of reconstruction*: Norton Library New York, p. 8.
- Madhok, B. (1972). *A story of Bungling in Kashmir*: New Delhi: Young Asia Publications, pp. 5-7.
- MD, G. (2017). Should Pakistan purchase the Wakhan Corridor from Afghanistan in the future? , from <https://www.quora.com/Should-Pakistan-purchase-the-Wakhan-Corridor-from-Afghanistan-in-the-future>
- Mustafa, Z. (1972). The Sino-Pakistan border: Historical aspect. *Pakistan Horizon*, 25(2), 43-50.
- Naz, A. S. (2012). *Gilgit State*: Gul Bakowlies Publications Airport Road Kashrote Gilgit, p. 60.
- Nazir, M. (2005). *Mutalah Shomaal (Study of North)*. : Universal Enterprisers Rawalpindi, p. 78.
- Omrani, B. (2009). The Durand line: History and problems of the Afghan-Pakistan border. *Asian Affairs*, 40(2), 177-195.
- Rasool, G. (2004). *Azadi-e-Gilgit-Baltistan (Liberation of Gilgit-Baltistan)*: One International Publishers Rawalpindi, pp. 19-21/181-190.
- Report, S. (24th January 2020). CPEC is in Pakistan's 'best interest,' says Qureshi amid US criticism, *Pakistan Today*. Retrieved from <https://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2020/01/23/pakistan-to-serve-its-interests-says-queshi-amid-us-criticism-of-cpec/>
- Rubin, M. (2002). Who is responsible for the Taliban. *Middle East review of international affairs*, 6(1), 1-16.
- Sandhu, K. K. (15th August 2016). Modi stumps Pakistan refers to Balochistan, Gilgit, and PoK from Red Fort. *India Today*. <https://www.indiatoday.in/india/delhi/story/modi-pakistan-balochistan-gilgit-pok-red-fort-335306-2016-08-15>.
- Šćekić, R. (2016). Geopolitical Strategies And Modernity: Multipolar World Of Nowadays. *Journal of Liberty and International Affairs*, 1(3), 84-92.
- Sing, G. (1986). *Gilgit 1947 Sy Pahly (Gilgit Before: 1947)* Hunny Sara Publishing Network Gilgit, pp. 33-34.
- Singh, J. (1995). *Pakistan occupied Kashmir under the Jackboot*: Siddhi Books, p. 22.
- Singh, P. (2013). *Gilgit Baltistan: between hope and despair*: New Delhi, India.
- Sökefeld, M. (2014). Anthropology of Gilgit-Baltistan: Introduction. *EthnoScripts: Zeitschrift für aktuelle ethnologische Studien*, 16(1), 9-29.

- Sōkefeld, M. (2005). From colonialism to postcolonial colonialism: changing modes of domination in the Northern areas of Pakistan. *The journal of Asian studies*, 64(4), 939-973.
- Sood, V. (2016). The strategic importance of Gilgit Baltistan. *ORF commentaries*.
- Venier, P. (2019). Mackinder's map of the natural seats of power (1904). *The Kaleidoscope of International Relations*. <https://medium.com/the-kaleidoscope-of-international-relations/the-map-of-the-natural-seats-of-power-1904-e341d4ce52a4>.
- Watson, F. (1966). *The frontiers of China*: Chatto & Windus, p. 25.
- Wolf, S. O. (2016). *China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and its impact on Gilgit-Baltistan*.
- Zain, O. F. (2010). A Socio-Political Study of Gilgit Baltistan Province. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 30(1).

Authors name and details:

Dr. Israr Hussain is a PhD scholar of International Politics from Shanghai International Studies University (SISU), Shanghai, China. His research areas are Geopolitics, China-Pakistan Relations, China's Belt and Road Initiative, China-Pakistan Economic Corridor. Email: isrargbpak@gmail.com

Professor Hu Lizhong is a PhD scholar and senior professor of Shanghai International Studies University (SISU), Shanghai, China His research area is Ideas and Practice of Chinese Foreign Relations. Email: hu_lz@shisu.edu.cn

Dr. Iqtidar Hussain is a PhD scholar of International Politics from Shanghai International Studies University (SISU), Shanghai,. His research areas are Regional Politics, Regional integration, Political Economy, Geopolitics, China-South Asia Relations, China's Belt and Road Initiative, China-Pakistan Economic Corridor. Email: qambarih@shisu.edu.cn

Mr. Iqrar Hussain Qambari is a research scholar of Karakorum International University (KIU), Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan. Email: iqrarqambari@gmail.com

Acknowledgments

All praises and thanks be to God Almighty. Special thanks to Prof. Dr. Hu Lizhong, School of International Relations and Public Affairs, Shanghai International Studies University (SISU), No, 550 Dalian west Road, Postcode 200083, Shanghai, China

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. USA ,NY ,TWASP. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info